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ABSTRACTS

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Phytochemical Screening and Biological Assay of Pods of *Cassia fistula*

Pooja Rana

MIT School of Bioengineering Sciences & Research, MIT Art, Design and Technology University, Loni Kalbhor, Pune

Corresponding author: pooja.rana@mituniversity.edu.in

Abstract: *Cassia fistula* Linn., commonly known as 'Golden Shower', has been a treasure trove of healing compounds in various traditional medicines across Asia for centuries. The pods of *Cassia fistula* house an impressive array of biologically active compounds, including anthraquinones, flavonoids, alkaloids, tannins, and many more, which modern medicine eagerly seeks to harness for their remarkable medical benefits. Advanced techniques like HPLC, MS are employed to identify and quantify these compounds, making the pods of *Cassia fistula* a promising candidate for anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antidiabetic, and other therapeutic applications. In the present study, the anti-inflammatory and antioxidant potential of pods of *C. fistula* was investigated. The phytochemical analysis confirmed the presence of alkaloids, saponins, flavonoids, anthraquinones, phenolic compounds, carbohydrate, fats, proteins and amino acids. The TFC (Total Flavonoid content) and TPC (Total Phenolic Content) in the methanolic extract of *Cassia fistula* was found to be 0.117mg GAE /g dry weight and 0.278 mg Rutin/g dry weight respectively. The antioxidant activity determined using 2, 2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) assay confirmed the scavenging activity with percent inhibition of 54.43 and FRAP (Ferric ion Reducing Antioxidant Power) reducing ability showed 88.88 equivalent mmol of Fe²⁺/g reducing potential. The methanolic extract of the pod inhibited the heat induced albumin denaturation in a concentration dependent manner and maximum inhibition observed was 81.71% at concentration of 150 µg/ml. The extract of *C. fistula* was effective in stabilizing the membrane of RBC by precluding the discharge of lytic enzymes and other active inflammatory mediators. At concentration of 150 µg/ml the extract showed 85.18% heat-induced haemolysis of RBC membrane. Based on the accumulated results, the presence of phytochemicals within the *C. fistula* extract has potential therapeutic efficacy and plays dynamic role in various biological activities.

Keywords: Secondary metabolites, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant.

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Rajbaug, Next to Hadapsar, Loni Kalbhor, Pune 412201, India.

+91 744 7444 027 / 28 | +91 914 6051 841 / 42

www.mitbio.edu.in / icrtb@mituniversity.edu.in

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